

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023
ISSN: 3026-9733

Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D

Russia-Ukraine Conflict: An Examination of its Impact on Food Security in Nigeria

¹Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D, ²Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D Candidate

¹Department of Political Science and Public Administration
University of Uyo, Uyo
Phone: 080223589264

Email: udoeyo84@gmail.com

²Department of Political Science and Public Administration
University of Uyo, Uyo
080692122110

ABSTRACT

The commonly held belief around the world was that the worldwide financial sanctions put on Russia, as well as the seizure of the property and assets of President Putin's billionaire friends would damage the Russian economy and hamper any further the war on Ukraine. This was a rational thought, but the issue has extended across the global economy. This article explores the Russian occupation of Ukraine and Nigeria's food security. The study conducted a timeline analysis to illustrate the major events that preceded and happened during the conflict. This necessitates the utilization of multiple scholarly and media reports in order to give a vivid analysis of the events and its repercussions for the world at large, and Nigeria in particular. The purpose of this study is to assess the consequences of Russia-Ukraine war in 2022 on significant global economic sectors and food security in Nigeria. The Realist Theory was employed in this study to examine the origins of the crisis. Experts expect a negative impact on household consumption, heightened uncertainty, erratic stock swings, supply chain disruptions, increasing utility prices, reduced investment owing to political dangers, and economic growth challenges. It is also crucial for politicians across the world to look into alternate ways to ensure survival if Russia responds by reducing its export of essential global commodities such as oil, natural gas, wheat, neon, titanium, palladium, and ammonium nitrate, for which it is a significant export leader.

Keyword: Conflict; Food security; Global economy; Inflation; War

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

Introduction

At the onset of 2022, there was a prevailing sense of optimism over global economic recovery following the COVID-19 pandemic. This sentiment was fueled by the efforts of various nations to address mounting inflationary pressures and implement strategies aimed at stimulating economic expansion. As a consequence, there has been a shift towards a more positive evaluation of the global gross domestic product (GDP), with projections indicating a projected increase of 4.4% in 2022 according to the International Monetary Fund (2022). In February 2022, Ukraine was subjected to a military incursion by Russia. The conflict escalated political instability between Russia and Western nations, hence diminishing global economic prospects due to apprehensions regarding the crisis' effects on the worldwide supply chain.

The topic of Ukraine's sovereignty continued to be a subject of debate following the Independence vote in December 1991, primarily due to Russia's prolonged and stated hesitation (Dragneva, Lewers, and Wolczuk, 2016). In the aftermath of the disintegration of the communist system, the Eastern European countries that were previously under the influence of the Soviet Union have undergone a deliberate process of integration into Western institutions, notably the European Union (EU) and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). In contrast, Russia did not endorse the Maiden revolutionary uprising that resulted in the removal of the democratically elected Yanukovich government and the strengthening of Ukraine's alignment with Western nations (Pabriks and Kudors, 2015). The Western world has often emphasized Russia's hostility towards Ukraine (Charap and Darden, 2014). From Russia's standpoint, Ukraine held significant importance, leading Russians to perceive its breakup as inherently abnormal. Numerous prominent historians, political scientists, academicians, journalists, and government officials have expressed the need for thorough examination of Russia-Ukraine ties, with a special emphasis on understanding the Ukrainian perspective (Sol'canyk, 2001).

Since the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the bilateral relationship between Ukraine and Russia has been characterized by a typicality, volatility, and conflict, as Kyiv and Moscow hold divergent viewpoints. The following concerns have affected the Ukrainian-Russian relationship: formal Soviet Union asset/debt disposal; Ukraine's

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

considerable energy debt; NATO's eastward expansion, border demarcation between both states; and the position of the Russian minority in Ukraine (Sol'canyk, 2001). Malyarenko and Wolff (2018) assert that Russia strategically employs violent civil conflicts among nations situated in the Near Abroad region as a means to augment its authority in the post-Soviet sphere while simultaneously diminishing the influence of Western powers. The city of Moscow demonstrates a preference for cultivating amicable and stable relationships with its neighboring regions while actively avoiding the prospect of a pleasant yet assertively pro-Western neighboring environment. These authors also draw attention to the vulnerability of Ukraine as the country continues to experience pressure from multiple directions, including the European Union and NATO from the western side, and Russia from the eastern side. Additionally, Ukraine has internal challenges such as a socioeconomic catastrophe, inadequate institutional structures, and internal divisions. The protest that took place in Ukraine at the end of 2013 as a result of the government's decision to reject a new agreement with the European Union, garnered significant international attention and posed considerable obstacles to the country's sovereignty, thereby ultimately contributing to heightened domestic instability. The demonstration ultimately led to President Yanukovich's departure from Ukraine, as well as Russia's annexation of Crimea and its support for separatist groups in eastern Ukraine in order to protect the ethnic Russian population (Korovkin and Makarin, 2019).

The events that unfolded in 2014 in Ukraine had significant consequences, including the removal of President Viktor Yanukovich, who was known for his close ties with Russia. Also, the interim administration took a significant step towards European Union (EU) membership by signing a trade agreement in February. Furthermore, Russia's annexation of Crimea took place in April of that year; and the Minsk Accord, a cease-fire agreement, was signed by Russia, Ukraine, France, and Germany during the period of 2014 and 2015. Subsequently, in April 2019, Volodymyr Zelensky, a former comedian, was elected as the President of Ukraine (Bigg, 2022).

In January 2021, President Zelensky made a formal request for Ukraine's inclusion in NATO, prompting Russia to deploy a significant number of troops near Ukraine's border, ostensibly for a training exercise. This development has led to

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023
ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

escalating tensions among Western nations, Russia, and Ukraine, ultimately culminating in Russia's invasion of Ukraine on February 24, 2022 - an operation tagged by Russians as "special military operations." Following the latest attack, Ukraine's Western allies have implemented stringent financial sanctions against Russia. These measures include imposing restrictions on Russia's central bank and excluding crucial banks from the principal global system of payment (Aloisi and Daniel, 2022). The ongoing crisis in Ukraine coincides with the obstacles faced by African nations in their efforts to recover from the disruptive consequences of the global COVID-19 pandemic. This pandemic has resulted in severe economic setbacks, substantial declines in productivity, exacerbated disparities, heightened environmental concerns, and in certain instances, security issues. The aforementioned situations pose significant risks to the progress of African development, hence exacerbating the challenges in achieving the objectives of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals and the African Union's Agenda 2063.

The crisis in Nigeria and Africa in entirety has resulted in various direct effects, including trade interruption, escalation in food and fuel prices, unstable macroeconomic conditions, and security concerns. In a notable occurrence not witnessed before 2014, the crisis triggered a surge in the value of a barrel of Brent oil, surpassing the \$100 threshold. Concurrently, there was a notable increase in food grain prices due to supply interruptions originating from Russia and Ukraine, which had a significant impact on global markets. These disruptions, both current and anticipated, had a profound effect on the pricing dynamics of food grains worldwide. In the majority of African nations, food and gasoline constitute over 33% of the consumer price index. The forthcoming inflation is anticipated to exhibit rapid and severe characteristics, notably affecting vulnerable demographics such as women and children.

Additionally, it is crucial to take into account the indirect consequences of the crisis - the occurrence of imported inflation, the complexities associated with energy transitions, and the possibility of geopolitical realignment. In order to effectively achieve diversification, Europe will be need to seek out alternative suppliers to fulfill the other two-thirds of the deficit. Gas producers in Africa, namely Algeria, Libya, and Nigeria, possess advantageous positioning to address this vacuum. Nevertheless, the augmented global demand for oil and gas has two immediate consequences. First, it is important to consider that this could potentially undermine efforts to achieve a fair and smooth transition towards environmentally sustainable energy sources. Also, the

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

exportation of gas supplies from African countries to Europe has the potential to restrict the availability of natural gas on the continent in the immediate period.

The ongoing conflict possesses the capacity to precipitate significant debt challenges for Nigeria and Africa, hence diminishing the likelihood of countries fulfilling their loan repayment commitments. Additionally, it is important to consider that heightened food and fuel costs might exacerbate inequality, as they tend to have a disproportionate impact on households who are already vulnerable. The limited availability of power and cooking gas will result in an increase in multidimensional poverty among households. Additionally, households facing budget constraints may be compelled to sell their possessions, therefore diminishing their capacity to mitigate future adversities. In general, the indirect consequences discussed above are likely to exert a detrimental influence on the overall economic activity and may give rise to social conflicts and instability. With the aforementioned objective in mind, this study aims to examine the impact of the Russia-Ukraine War on the cost of oil and gas, as well as food security in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Since the incursion of Russian tanks into Ukraine on February 24, 2022, there has been a discernible escalation in global fragility, exacerbating divisions in world security and peace, and eroding relations between Russia and Western nations. The current situation is a matter of significant concern not just for Russia and Ukraine, but also for African economies, giving rise to serious apprehensions. The war has had a discernible effect on various sectors, particularly in terms of increased energy and food expenses resulting from disruptions in the supply chain and trade networks attributable to the conflict. Despite numerous attempts made by the international community to mitigate and bring an end to the ongoing Russia-Ukraine conflict, it persists; and despite the implementation of stringent sanctions by Western nations, coupled with several dialogues between leaders of Russia and Ukraine, the conflict persists (Song and Zhou, 2020).

The prospects of global economic recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to a significant decline in GDP growth by approximately 3.5% in 2020, are currently being delayed as a result of the escalating conflict between Russia and Ukraine. This exacerbates the challenges faced by the global economy, with a particular impact on African economies within the context of the pandemic. The conflict has

Evolution of the Russian-Ukrainian Military Conflict

The Western perspective posits that Russia's invasion can be attributed to perceived threats emanating from Ukraine. Ukraine, a nation that has embraced liberalization, actively pursues collaborations with Western nations in areas such as trade, security, and politics. This includes the potential for affiliations with NATO and the EU, which are viewed as jeopardizing Russia's national security. Consequently, Russia's military intervention is seen as an attempt to set up a new Ukrainian government that aligns with Russian interests. However, it might be argued that Russia's rationale for its invasion stems from the perception that Western powers are exploiting Ukraine's influence. Moreover, Russia has employed its military forces to suppress those residing in separatist territories who exhibit loyalty to the Russian government while also engaging in acts that can be characterized as genocidal towards its own populace. The Russian government has asserted that Ukraine's aspiration to become part of the NATO military alliance presents a significant challenge to Russia's national security. This is due to the potential geographical proximity of NATO to Russia's borders, which is perceived as an existential threat by Russia (AERO TIME 2022).

Russia and Ukraine share a significant historical background and maintained strong ties until the year 2014. The protracted conflict initiated by the incursion into Crimea in February 2014, has endured for a duration of eight years. In November 2013, the Ukrainian government, under the leadership of President Viktor Yanukovich who held pro-Russian views, declined a proposed agreement to become a member of the European Union (EU). The aforementioned denial served as the catalyst for the Euro maiden demonstrations that took place in Independence Square, the capital of Ukraine, Kyiv. On the 27th and 28th of February, 2014, there was an occurrence of pro-Russian militants conducting raids and subsequently taking control of various buildings in Simferopol, the capital city of Crimea. On February 28, 2014, particularly, a group of unidentified individuals armed with firearms appeared in the vicinity of the primary airport in Crimea. On February 24, 2022, the global community was taken aback by an unexpected event. Vladimir Putin's actions have been perceived as disruptive to the stability of Europe since he initiated a conflict against the democratic principles upheld

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

intensified global inflation and obscured the international economic forecast. In April, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) revised its projections, showing a decrease in global growth from 6.1% in 2021 to 3.6% in both 2022 and 2023. These figures are 0.8 and 0.2 percentage points lower, respectively, compared to the January estimates provided by the IMF (IMF, 2022).

Before the onset of the conflict, Africa was experiencing a state of prolonged transition characterized by a slower recovery from the COVID-19 pandemic. The current conflict poses a significant risk of undoing the progress that had been achieved. The persistently low vaccination rates in Africa remain a significant concern as highlighted by Duho et al. (2021) and the World Health Organization Africa (2021). Consequently, this conflict has already resulted in a shift of global focus away from the pandemic's repercussions on the continent. Unfortunately, attention has been redirected towards rearmament efforts, leading to the diversion of substantial financial resources from other pressing matters related to sustainable development. Several European nations such as Germany, Belgium, Romania, Italy, Poland, Norway, and Sweden, have increased their military expenditures, while limiting investments in factors that promote long-term and sustainable economic development. Contrarily, it is worth noting that affluent nations possess the advantage of accessing financial facilities with exceptionally low interest rates to support their efforts in recovering from the pandemic, while impoverished developing nations are faced with the burden of allocating substantial funds towards servicing their debts. This impedes their ability to fully dedicate themselves to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN DESA, 2022).

The final verdict about the outcome of these events remains uncertain, and it is anticipated that the vulnerabilities of African economies will exacerbate in light of the prevailing circumstances. The escalation of energy and food expenses has resulted in a surge in inflation rates, heightened concerns regarding food insecurity, disruptions in trade activities, reduced levels of investment, and a decline in the overall GDP growth within the African continent. The conflict is expected to yield severe economic ramifications for impoverished households on a global scale, with a special emphasis on low-income nations in Africa. According to Salyer et al. (2021), if the ongoing conflict between Russia and Ukraine persists until 2023, it would have catastrophic implications for the continent. This is because the progress made in attaining Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) targets will be negated.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

by a population of 44 million individuals. His rationale for this military engagement was based on the belief that Ukraine's alignment with Western values poses an ongoing risk to Russia's security, progress, and survival.

The EU and Ukraine

The European Union (EU), formerly confined to Western Europe, is a supranational entity consisting of 28 European nations governed by shared economic, social, and security frameworks. The European Union initiated a comprehensive process of integration into the Central and Eastern European region throughout the early years of the twenty-first century. The European Union, formerly referred to as the European Economic Community and the European Atomic Energy Community, was founded in 1957 by a coalition of six nations, namely Belgium, Germany, France, Italy, Luxembourg, and the Netherlands (Jawad et al., 2021). In the year 2004, the European Union had a momentous expansion marked by the accession of ten new member states to the union. Croatia became the most recent member of the organization in the year 2013. In 2014, the European Union (EU) and Ukraine entered into an Association Agreement (AA) commonly referred to as the "EU-Ukraine Association Agreement." This agreement signifies a significant milestone in the progression of contractual relations between the EU and Ukraine, aiming to foster political affiliation and economic integration. Ukraine has undertaken a commitment to implement economic, legal, and financial reforms with the aim of harmonizing its laws and regulations with those of the European Union. Ukraine has made a commitment to gradually adopt and apply technical and consumer standards established by the European Union. On February 22, 2014, subsequent to the dissolution of a power-sharing agreement, the Ukrainian government established a novel administration.

The 2014 Crimea Invasion

In March 2014, a group of unidentified military people, later confirmed to be Russian forces, launched an assault on and subsequently took over the autonomous assembly of the Crimean peninsula. On March 6, the Crimean parliament made the decision to break away from Ukraine and join the Russian Federation. A public referendum was scheduled

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

to take place on March 16, 2014. The move received praise in Russia, while it faced significant criticism in Western countries. The annexation law signed by Russian President Vladimir Putin on March 21, 2014, resulted in the formal integration of Crimea into Russia, a status that remains in effect at present. As per scholarly analysis, the aforementioned event can be regarded as the most significant acquisition of land in Europe since the conclusion of World War II in 1945. This occurrence is deemed to contravene fundamental tenets of international law and accords, hence undermining the territorial integrity of Ukraine (Merezhko, 2015).

Ukraine, NATO and the 2022 Russia Invasion

The North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) was founded in 1949 with the participation of the United States, Canada, and many Western European nations. Its primary objective was to ensure collective security and defense against the Soviet Union. Since its establishment, the organization has employed political and military strategies to safeguard the autonomy and safety of its constituents. The pursuit of this objective is achieved by a focus on collective defense, crisis management, and the formulation of corporate security policy. A fundamental differentiating principle of NATO is the notion that any aggression directed at one or multiple member states is regarded as an assault on the collective entity as a whole. NATO membership is accessible to European nations, and in recent times, more members such as North Macedonia in 2020 have been admitted, while other nations such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, and Ukraine have expressed their desire for membership. According to Bekkers and Koopman (2022), Sweden and Finland are actively pursuing membership in NATO.

The primary source of contention revolves around Ukraine's bid for NATO membership. On the other hand, Russia has voiced concerns over potential encroachment on its political influence due to the shared border with Ukraine, particularly in light of the prospective inclusion of Eastern European nations into NATO. Russia therefore, asserts that Ukraine should not be granted membership in NATO due to these encroachment concerns. To abate this, a formal request was made by Russia to Western nations, urging them to offer a legally enforceable promise that NATO will refrain from engaging in any military activities within Eastern Europe or Ukraine. Notwithstanding these expectations, Ukraine has been actively endeavoring to accelerate the NATO admissions process with the aim of drawing lessons from Russia's

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

invasion of Crimea in 2014. Persistent tensions have been observed between the two erstwhile republics over an extended period of time. In January 2021, there was a notable escalation of hostilities when Ukrainian President, Volodymyr Zelenskyy advocated for the inclusion of Ukraine in NATO, urging US President, Joe Biden to extend an invitation. The aforementioned proposal elicited strong displeasure from Russia, prompting the mobilization of military forces in close proximity to the Ukrainian border. The military incursion and subsequent conflict in Ukraine were evidently conducted, with Belarus serving as a transit route (Gunay and Can, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Realist Theory

According to Faleti (2006), realist theory may be traced back to classical political theory, which was aimed at elucidating the origins of conflict by attributing them to inherent flaws in human nature that result in self-interest and pursuit of power for personal gains. The theory of international relations places significant stress on the central role of the state (state-centrism), the pursuit of national interest, and the use of power within the context of global politics and the establishment of order. Carr (1939) and Morgenthau (1948) put forth a theoretical framework aimed at elucidating the behaviour of states and offering a range of policy options for a comprehensive analysis of the exercise of state power in the realms of foreign policy and diplomatic studies. Waltz (1979) and Donnelly (2005) also made notable scholarly contributions to the realist theoretical framework as it pertains to internal interactions. The theory is categorized into three main branches based on scholars' comprehension of the underlying reasons for inter-state conflicts. According to classical realist theory, conflict emerges as a consequence of inherent human nature and subsequently manifests itself. Neo-realists credit it to the dynamics of the anarchic state system, whereas neoclassical realists attribute it to a combination of both the anarchic state system and domestic politics.

Faleti (2006) argues that this theory has provided substantial support for the militarization of international relations, the arms race, and the subsequent elevation of power and the state to an ideological status, significantly influencing international conflicts. This theory additionally offers conceptual and analytical perspectives on the reasons behind governments' establishment of armies and, in certain circumstances, their pursuit of nuclear weapons, even if solely for the sake of deterrence. According to Riley (2008), the theoretical paradigm of realism holds significant utility in the analysis

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

of contemporary battles within the global arena. The theory of realism places significant emphasis on the steadfast position of sovereign nations within the global arena, notwithstanding its limitations in comprehensively accounting for the emergence and expansion of non-state actors and militant revolutionary organizations.

According to this theoretical framework, nation-states adopt a strategy of self-reliance to safeguard their ongoing existence by emphasizing power dynamics specifically measured by their military might. It is noteworthy that they exhibit a lack of recognition towards global institutions that endeavour to foster economic cooperation. The objective of this study, as stated earlier, is to evaluate the consequences of the decline in overt displays of military power, which leads to the implementation of diverse international sanctions that affect the economic prosperity of both vulnerable and, in certain instances, advanced nations. The phenomenon of inflation affecting various commodities and services in both industrialized and emerging nations serves as a compelling illustration. In contemporary times, the theory of realism continues to serve as a pragmatic framework for scholarly examination due to its ability to elucidate the behaviours of states as influential actors within the global system. This will result in nation-states persistence in enhancing their military capacities to safeguard the continuous survival of the state.

Empirical Study

Prior scholarly investigations on the economic ramifications of warfare have consistently revealed that armed conflicts provide significant economic implications. According to several academic experts, there exist two distinct ideological perspectives concerning the consequences of armed conflicts. The school of thought known as "war renewal" argues that war can yield positive outcomes such as diminishing the influence of powerful interest groups, fostering innovation, and enhancing economic efficiency through the development of human capital. This perspective aligns with Keynesian economic theory. Conversely, the "ruins of war" school of thought perceives war as a catastrophic event devoid of any economic advantages (Kang and Meernik, 2005). It has also been observed by other experts that nations with lower economic status are more prone to the occurrence of civil conflicts, particularly in instances where they are confronted with adverse fluctuations in revenue (Chassang and Miquel, 2009).

In the study conducted by Koubi (2005), an assessment was made about the

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

influence of international military conflicts on the economic growth of major nations during the period spanning 1960 and 1989. This study revealed that the variations in economic growth among countries are intricately linked to the characteristics and occurrence of war. Based on empirical research, there exists a positive correlation between postwar economic output and the extent and length of the conflict. Furthermore, the impact of this relationship on economic growth varies inversely with the level of economic development within a given country. In their study, Kang and Meernik (2005) conducted an evaluation of the effects of civil war on multiple economies spanning the years 1960 and 2002. It was found that the occurrence of war exerts an adverse impact on economic fundamentals, while the response of the international community to civil wars holds considerable sway over economic growth.

Methodology

This qualitative study employed a descriptive research design to examine the progression of the military conflicts between Russia and Ukraine, as well as the underlying motivations behind Russia's assault on Ukraine from the perspectives of pro-Western and pro-Russian factions. Additionally, the study sought to explore the ramifications of these conflicts on global economies, with a specific focus on its impact on Nigeria. The investigation relied on credible media reports and statements made by leaders of the conflicting parties. The observation of documentary evidence dealing with the Russia-Ukraine situation was used to obtain data for this study. Secondary sources included books, journals, articles, periodicals, government reports and publications, magazines, unpublished manuscripts, commentaries, and conference papers. Other information was gathered from electronic sources such as television news broadcasts, radio news broadcasts, and Internet publications.

Results and discussion of Findings

The present surge in global market prices for primary food commodities has resemblance to the food crisis experienced in 2008, hence presenting a significant worldwide threat to food security. The current circumstances in Africa are notably grave as evidenced by the COVID-19 pandemic and the more recent Russia-Ukraine crisis.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

These events have highlighted the susceptibility of food systems to significant disruptions, particularly in nations such as Nigeria that significantly depend on the importation of essential staple commodities like rice and wheat.

Nigeria is currently faced with several challenges that pose a threat to its already fragile food security. The escalation of global food prices and the disruption of supply, particularly of wheat, oils, and other essential products, exacerbates these concerns. This is mostly due to the fact that more than half of the food consumed by households in Nigeria is obtained through purchases

Concurrently, Nigeria's capacity to produce essential commodities such as fertilizers and natural gas, presents an opportunity for the country to leverage global market disturbances resulting from the crisis. This article examines the potential impact of the Russia-Ukraine conflict on food insecurity in Nigeria, in addition to the opportunities that may arise for the country in the growing fertilizer and energy industries.

Nigeria's Wheat Imports (2020-2022)

Nigeria serves as a significant importer and user of wheat-based commodities. As reported by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), wheat is the third most consumed grain in Nigeria following maize and rice. However, local production only contributes to a mere 1% of the annual consumption of 5 to 6 million metric tons. Based on the data at hand, it can be observed that Nigeria experienced a significant surge in its wheat imports in 2020, with a value exceeding \$2.15 billion. This represents a notable 40% growth compared to the preceding year. Consequently, Nigeria has secured its position as the fourth-largest global importer of wheat, trailing behind Egypt, China, and Turkey. It is noteworthy that wheat has emerged as the primary item on Nigeria's import expenditure, surpassing petroleum products such as petrol and diesel. Furthermore, it is crucial to acknowledge that wheat stands as the most imported food item within the Nigerian market as reported by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in 2021. In the year 2020, Russia held the position of the second-largest provider of wheat imports, with a total value of \$401 million, placing it behind the United States, which held the leading position with a value of \$518 million.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

Nigeria's import dependency is expected to persist due to fundamental challenges like inadequate adoption of agricultural technologies that could boost yields, sluggish advancements in research and development in the agricultural sector, and the occurrence of climate-induced disasters and violent conflicts. As an illustration, it can be observed that the nation's agricultural output of essential crops such as cereals, falls short in meeting the domestic food requirements. Specifically, approximately 99% of the wheat consumed in Nigeria is imported, while a significant portion of the annual rice consumption, amounting to two million metric tons out of seven million metric tons, is acquired through illicit means including smuggling across land borders. It is worthy of note that this occurs despite the existence of an official prohibition on rice imports in Nigeria. Consequently, prior to the occurrence of the COVID-19 epidemic and the accompanying Russia-Ukraine crisis, the nation's food security was vulnerable to fluctuations in global food prices. Nigeria's vulnerability stems from its persistent dependence on import restrictions and regulations as a means to promote domestic food production, a practice that frequently leads to elevated costs for both imported and local food commodities (World Bank, 2022).

Increase in price has emerged as a significant concern in the context of the outbreak. According to the World Bank Nigeria's and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Nigeria's National Longitudinal Phone Survey conducted in 2020 showed a significant increase in food costs subsequent to the onset of the COVID-19 epidemic. The inflation rate of key food items experienced a significant increase of 23% in March 2021, marking the highest level observed in the prior two years (NBS, 2021). Recent data provided by NBS indicates that food price inflation has continued into March 2022.

Recent research utilizing comprehensive and prolonged monthly data on food prices has revealed a substantial increase in the cost of various food commodities throughout the pandemic. Notably, imported rice and wheat experienced significant price hikes of 41% and 21% respectively (Amare et al., 2022). This paper is an analysis of the fluctuation of wheat prices in Nigeria, examining both the national trend and the average prices among the country's six geopolitical zones. Before the onset of the pandemic, the levels and variability of wheat prices remained relatively stable. The onset of the outbreak led to a notable 21% increase in wheat prices at a national level, accompanied by a substantial rise in price dispersion across other marketplaces.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

Nigeria's import dependency is expected to persist due to fundamental challenges like inadequate adoption of agricultural technologies that could boost yields, sluggish advancements in research and development in the agricultural sector, and the occurrence of climate-induced disasters and violent conflicts. As an illustration, it can be observed that the nation's agricultural output of essential crops such as cereals, falls short in meeting the domestic food requirements. Specifically, approximately 99% of the wheat consumed in Nigeria is imported, while a significant portion of the annual rice consumption, amounting to two million metric tons out of seven million metric tons, is acquired through illicit means including smuggling across land borders. It is worthy of note that this occurs despite the existence of an official prohibition on rice imports in Nigeria. Consequently, prior to the occurrence of the COVID-19 epidemic and the accompanying Russia-Ukraine crisis, the nation's food security was vulnerable to fluctuations in global food prices. Nigeria's vulnerability stems from its persistent dependence on import restrictions and regulations as a means to promote domestic food production, a practice that frequently leads to elevated costs for both imported and local food commodities (World Bank, 2022).

Increase in price has emerged as a significant concern in the context of the outbreak. According to the World Bank Nigeria's and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Nigeria's National Longitudinal Phone Survey conducted in 2020 showed a significant increase in food costs subsequent to the onset of the COVID-19 epidemic. The inflation rate of key food items experienced a significant increase of 23% in March 2021, marking the highest level observed in the prior two years (NBS, 2021). Recent data provided by NBS indicates that food price inflation has continued into March 2022.

Increase in price has emerged as a significant concern in the context of the outbreak. According to the World Bank Nigeria's and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), the Nigeria's National Longitudinal Phone Survey conducted in 2020 showed a significant increase in food costs subsequent to the onset of the COVID-19 epidemic. The inflation rate of key food items experienced a significant increase of 23% in March 2021, marking the highest level observed in the prior two years (NBS, 2021). Recent data provided by NBS indicates that food price inflation has continued into March 2022.

Recent research utilizing comprehensive and prolonged monthly data on food prices has revealed a substantial increase in the cost of various food commodities throughout the pandemic. Notably, imported rice and wheat experienced significant

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleviv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

Furthermore, the upward trend in pricing has persisted over time.

The potential cessation of loans from China, a significant and frequent lender to developing nations, exacerbates the immediate consequences of food and energy constraints on low-income countries. In their recent study, Horn, Reinhart, and Trebesch (2022) present empirical evidence from a novel dataset, highlighting China's prominent role as a key participant in international sovereign debt renegotiations. However, the authors note that Chinese lenders rarely engage in substantial debt relief measures involving face value reduction, except for occasional symbolic debt cancellations pertaining to small zero-interest loans. Additionally, it is evident from the findings that China's offshore credit expansion, which spanned several years, had mostly concluded before to the conflict and had been further intensified as a result of it. According to the findings presented by McGuirk and Burke (2022), the implications have significant weight. The extent of the impact differs significantly based on the respective net positions of individual countries. Net exporting countries tend to enjoy increased prosperity and decreased levels of conflict, whereas countries that rely on imports for food and energy are more prone to experiencing issues such as hunger, suffering, food-related uprisings, and an escalation in inter-group aggression.

Conclusion

The ongoing conflict between Russia and Ukraine poses a significant threat to the accessibility of numerous agricultural products in countries heavily dependent on this region. The commodity market experienced a notable surge during the commencement of the conflict in February 2022, and it is anticipated that prices would persistently rise in the forthcoming months. The phenomenon of global inflation is characterized by a persistent upward trend, hence posing potential threats to both humanitarian requirements and geopolitical stability. Ukraine and Russia have earned the moniker "Breadbasket of Europe" due to their significant contributions to the agricultural sector, encompassing the production of several commodities including sunflower seeds, cottonseed oil, wheat, barley, maize, and fertilizers. Prior to the onset of the war, numerous countries across the globe experienced a deficiency in their food supply as a consequence of the economic downturn resulting from the Pandemic. According to global experts, it is widely acknowledged that the Ukrainian conflict had a significant influence on the harvesting season due to the bombardment of crucial ports, infrastructure, and grain storage silos by Russian forces. The exacerbation of the issue has been attributed to the implementation of more stringent sanctions targeting Russian

traders and supply chains, along with the imposition of limitations on commercial routes in the Black Sea and the Sea of Azov.

Recommendations

Nigeria should prioritize the mitigation of its dependence on food imports, alongside addressing other underlying structural challenges, while simultaneously fostering enduring resilience against food crises and other unforeseen disruptions. This can be achieved by directing attention towards the three significant policy domains outlined as follows:

- i. To commence, the government has the potential to expedite the execution of the recently formulated National Agricultural Technology and Innovation Policy (NATIP, 2022-2027). This policy primarily emphasizes the advancement of technologies that enhance agricultural productivity, with a specific emphasis on wheat and other significant food grains. The NATIP encompasses various strategies aimed at promoting agricultural development, including the implementation of rapid mechanisation, the establishment of an Agricultural Development Fund, the revitalisation of extension services, the enhancement of livestock and fisheries sectors, the promotion of market development, and the reinforcement of value chains. It is suggested that the initiation of NATIP implementation should commence with a prioritization exercise, wherein the estimation of the potential benefits of different policy options is conducted. These benefits should be evaluated in terms of poverty reduction, enhancements in agricultural productivity, and other urgent objectives. This approach will enable the effective resolution of both immediate crises and enduring challenges.
- ii. Additionally, it is recommended that the government consider revising inequitable agricultural trade rules. The recent resumption of land border operations represents a favourable progression. These approaches would effectively reduce the susceptibility of Nigerian households to fluctuations in food prices by enhancing the significance of markets in alleviating disruptions in supply. The resolution of trade barriers is of utmost importance for Nigeria's

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

*Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D*

- active participation and effective implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA). In light of the prevailing inflationary trends, it is prudent to consider reassessing the existing import restrictions on rice and chicken meat, among other commodities. Several crucial food commodities such as maize, sugar, and milk, continue to be included in the inventory of things that are either prohibited or subject to restrictions, or are deemed ineligible for imports through foreign exchange.
- iii. Thirdly, our study has highlighted other domains in which the global crisis may potentially yield advantageous outcomes for Nigeria. The initial findings derived from IFPRI's analysis of the impacts of ongoing global market disruptions suggest that Nigeria's economic progress in 2022 will be positively influenced by the escalation in natural gas prices. Conversely, the rise in food and fertiliser prices is projected to have an adverse impact on the country's growth. In order to enhance the economic resilience of Nigeria, it is imperative to leverage the country's comparative advantages, explore potential export markets such as fertiliser, and make strategic investments in infrastructure development to maximize the production of valuable resources like natural gas.
 - iv.) Ministers of Energy and policymakers ought to implement explicit policies aimed at expediting the progress of food security development in the continent. This approach is necessary to address the energy predicaments arising from the region's over dependence on fossil fuels, as exemplified by the escalating costs of oil and gas. In order to diminish the continent's dependence on fossil fuel imports, it is imperative to allocate substantial resources towards the revitalization of our refineries. This can be achieved by providing adequate incentives to facilitate the shift away from fossil fuels, while simultaneously making substantial investments in renewable energy sources and enhancing energy efficiency measures.
 - v.) In order to mitigate the issue, it is advisable for authorities to exercise caution when adjusting their policy rates in response to inflationary pressures. This should be done while considering the supply-side factors that are contributing to the significant increase in prices. In order to choose the most effective policy

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023
ISSN: 3026-9733

Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsirikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D

measures for their particular jurisdictions, it is imperative for decision-makers to carefully evaluate the trade-offs associated with each potential course of action.

References

- AERO TIME (2022). EU Bans the Sales of Aircraft to Russian Airlines. Available at: <https://www.aerotime.aero/articles/30329-eu-bans-sales-ofaircraft-torussian-airlines>. Accessed on: 12/04/2022.
- Aloisi, S. and Daniel, F. (2022). Timeline: The Events Leading up to Russia's Invasion of Ukraine. Reuters. Available at: <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/events-leading-up-russiasinvasion-ukraine-2022-02-2> Accessed on: 11/11/2022.
- Amare, M., Zemedu, L., Mehare, A and Bekele, K. (2022). The Impact of COVID 19, Vaccination and Non-pharmaceutical Policies on Ethiopian Trade: A Structural Gravity using Semi-parametric machine Learning. *Development Studies Research*, 9(1): 159-176.
- Bekkers, E. and Koopman, R. (2022). Simulating the Trade Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic: Scenario Analysis Based on Quantitative Trade Modeling. *The World Economy*, 45(2): 445-467.
- Bigg, M. (2022). A Timeline of the Tensions between Russia and Ukraine: The New York Times. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/2022/02/18/world/europe/russia-ukrainetimeline.html> Accessed on: 27/11/2022.
- Carr, E. (1939). *The twenty years' crisis 1919-1989: An introduction to the study of International Relations*. London. Retrieved from <https://www.pdfdrive.com/the-twenty-years-crisis-1919-1939-reissued-with-a-new-preface-from-michael-cox-e158074883.html>. Accessed on: 24/03/2023.
- Charap, S. and Darden, K. (2014). Russia and Ukraine. *Survival*, 56(2): 7-14.
- Chassang, S. and Miquel, P. (2009). Economic Shocks and Civil War. *Quarterly Journal of Political Science*, 4(3): 211-28.
- Donnelly, J. (2005). Realism. In: Burchill, S., Linklater, A., Devetak, R., Donnelly J., Paterson, M., Reus-Smith, C. & True, J. (2005) (Eds.). *Theories in International Relations*, (pp, 29-54). Palgrave-Macmillan.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023
ISSN: 3026-9733

Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D

- Dragneva-Lewers, R. and Wolczuk, K. (2016). *Ukraine between the EU and Russia: The Integration Challenge*. Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Duho, T., Taylor, A., Amamoo, S. and Amamoo, R. (2021). COVID-19 Vaccination, Supply Chain and Concerns on Vaccine Hesitancy in Africa. *The World Financial Review*, September/October Edition, 36-40.
- Faleti, S. (2006). Theories of social conflict. In Best, S. (2020). *Introduction to Peace and Conflict studies in West Africa*, pp. 35-60. Spectrum Books Limited.
- Gunay, S. and Can, G. (2022). The source of financial contagion and spillovers: An evaluation of the covid-19 pandemic and the global financial crisis. *PLoS ONE*, 17(1): e0261835.
- Horn, S., Reinhart, C. and Trebesch, C. (2022). China's overseas lending and the war in Ukraine. In: Garicano, L., Dominic Rohner, D. and Weder di Mauro, B. (eds.). *Global Economic Consequences of the War in Ukraine Sanctions, Supply Chains and Sustainability*. Centre for Economic Policy Research (CEPR) Press, London.
- International Monetary Fund (IMF) (2022). World Economic Outlook. Available at: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WEO/Issues/2022/01/25/world-economicoutlook-update-january-2022>. Accessed on: 09/01/2023.
- Jawad, M., Maroof, Z. and Naz, M. (2021). Impact of Pandemic COVID-19 on Global Economies (A Seven-Scenario Analysis). *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 42(7): 1897-1908.
- Kang, S. and Meernik, J. (2005). Civil War Destruction and the Prospects for Economic Growth. *The Journal of Politics*, 67(1): 88-109.
- Korovkin, V. and Makarin, A. (2019). Conflict and Inter-Group Trade: Evidence from the 2014 Russia/Ukraine Crisis: Available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_i Accessed on: 05/12/2022.
- Koubi, V. (2005). War and Economic Performance. *Journal of Peace Research*, 42(1): 67-82.
- Malyarenko, T. and Wolff, S. (2018). The Logic of Competitive Influence-seeking: Russia, Ukraine and the Conflict in Donbass. *Post-Soviet Affairs*, 34(4): 191-212.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 2, OCTOBER, 2023
ISSN: 3026-9733

Uko E. Uwak, Ph.D
& Nsikak Stephen Edet, Ph.D

- McGuirk, E. and Burke, M. (2022). War in Ukraine, world food prices, and conflict in Africa. In: Garicano, L., Dominic Rohner, D. and Weder di Mauro, B. (eds.). *Global Economic Consequences of the War in Ukraine Sanctions, Supply Chains and Sustainability*. Centre for Economic Policy Research (CEPR) Press, London.
- Merezhko, O. (2015). Crimea's Annexation by Russia—Contradictions of the New Russian Doctrine of International Law. *ZaoRV*, 75: 167-194.
- Morgenthau, H. (1948). *Politics among nations: The struggle for power and peace*. Retrieved from: <https://www.pdfdrive.com/politics-among-nations-the-struggle-for-power-and-peace-d158249064.html>. Accessed on: 24/03/2023.
- Pabriks, A. and Kudors, A. (2015). *The War in Ukraine: Lessons for Europe*. The Centre for East European Policy Studies.
- Riley, J. W. (2008). How Realistic is Realism? E-International Relations.
- Salyer, J., Maeda, J., Sembuche, S., Kebede, Y., Tshangela, A., Moussif, M., Ihekweazu, C., Mayet, N., Abate, E. and Ouma, A. (2021). The First and Second Waves of the COVID-19 Pandemic in Africa: A Cross-Sectional Study. *The Lancet*, 397(10281): 1265-1275.
- Sol'canyk, R. (2001). *Ukraine and Russia: The Post-Soviet Transition*. Rowman and Littlefield.
- Song, L. and Zhou, Y. (2020). The COVID-19 Pandemic and Its Impact on the Global Economy: What Does it Take to Turn Crisis into Opportunity? *China & World Economy*, 28(4): 1-25.
- UN DESA. (2022). Financing for Sustainable Development Report 2022. UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs. April.
- Waltz, K. (1979). *Theory of International Politics*. New York, McGraw-Hill.
- WHO Africa. (2021). Africa faces a 470 million COVID-19 Vaccine Shortfall in 2021. World Health Organization (WHO), Africa. Available at: <https://www.afro.who.int/news/africa-faces-470-million-covid-19-vaccineshortfall-2021>. Accessed on: 05/12/2022.
- World Bank (2022). *Commodity Markets Outlook*. World Bank: Washington DC.